

SOME GLIMPSES TO MUKIMI'S LITERARY WORLD

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Abstract: In this paper literary activity of the prominent poem and literary critic Mukimi is researched. Mukimi's literary activity is vast and his contribution to the development of Uzbek literature is of great value. These issues are analyzed in the paper.

Key words: Mukimi, poems, literary activity, literature, poet, ghazal, literary work, to criticize, stanza.

Mukimi, whose real name Muhammad Aminkhoja the son of Mirzakhoja, lived in 1850-1903, was a poet and a thinker. He is considered to be one of the founders of Uzbek democratic literature. He was born in Kokand. His father was from Tashkent, and his mother, Ayshabibi, was from Khojand. They lived in Kokand. Mukimi studied at Kokand and Bukhara madrasas. He was in Tashkent several times (1887–88, 1892, 1899). He lived in the Kokaldosh madrasa. He deeply studied the cultural and literary life of Tashkent. He creatively collaborated with advanced creative artists such as Almaiy, Nodim. He was in contact with Inomkhoja, one of the organizers of the Tashkent uprising of 1892, and wrote a poem dedicated to his death (1897).

He wrote mukhammas to the ghazals of Navai, Jami, Nizami, and Fuzuli. He considered Jami to be his mentor. He continued the traditions of Uzbek and Persian classical poets. The emergence and formation of the democratic direction in Uzbek literature is connected with the name of Mukimi. Such forward-thinking poets as Furkat, Zavki, Avaz, Kamil opened a new page in the history of Uzbek literature.

The conflict between the critical worldview and aspirations and the environment brought out a critical direction in his work. This is more reflected in his behavior. He created about 30 comic works on topics such as horses, carts, mud, flies, and malaria. In them, the poet criticized the backward and ugly aspects of life, defects in the social consciousness, the pain of colonialism, and described the desolation with venom ("Devonamen", "Ko'samen", "Hayron keridi loy", "Flies", "Complaint of malaria" and others). In a number of other satires, a new attitude to changes in the life of the society was reflected ("Definition of the oven", "Build the cart", "Mud", etc.).

Mukimi wrote a 4-part work "Travel logs" based on the impressions of his trips to different cities and villages. The work is written in a light, playful language and consists of 4-line stanzas. It realistically depicts the hardships in

people's lives and the destruction of villages. 10 poetic and about 20 prose letters of Mukimi have been saved. His poems have come down to us in manuscripts, collections, books published in lithography at the beginning of the 20th century, in the pages of periodical press printed in Tashkent and Petersburg.

One of the streets in Tashkent, the Uzbek State Musical Drama Theater, Yakkasaroy, Hamza districts are named after Mukimi. Sabir Abdulla wrote the novel "Mavlano Mukimi" and the drama "Mukimi" about him. Most of Mukimi's ghazals have been adapted into songs.

To conclude, it should be noted that Mukimi was one of the most outstanding and prominent poets of his period. His contribution to the development of Uzbek Literature has been prolific. That is one of the most essential reasons of commemorating the artist's works in every branch of literary life.

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